

Acoustic signatures of porous rocks permeated by partially-saturated, aligned planar fractures

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SUMMARY

The presence of sets of vertical, parallel fractures is very common in the Earth's upper crust. Notably, open fractures exert critical control on the mechanical and hydraulic properties of the host formation. There is great interest in understanding how fractures interact with seismic waves, as this knowledge could be used to detect and characterize fractures from seismic data. When a seismic wave travels through a fractured formation, it induces oscillatory fluid pressure diffusion (FPD) between the fractures and the embedding porous background, a physical process that produces attenuation and dispersion of the seismic wave. Although there are numerous studies on this topic, the case of parallel fractures saturated with different immiscible fluids, such as brine and CO₂, remains rather unexplored. With these motivations, in this work we propose an analytical approach to compute the phase velocity and attenuation of P-waves travelling perpendicularly to a set of planar, parallel fractures. While we consider that the background is saturated with brine, the fractures can be saturated with brine or gas. Our numerical analysis shows for the first time that two manifestations of FPD arise in these cases. One of them, associated with relatively high levels of attenuation, is due to FPD occurring between consecutive fractures saturated with different fluids. In this case, the FPD process is initiated at a frac-

ture saturated with brine and reaches a consecutive fracture saturated with gas. The other FPD manifestation, on the other hand, arises at higher frequencies, is characterized by lower levels of attenuation, and results from the interaction in the background of FPD processes initiated at consecutive fractures, irrespective of the fluid content. Finally, by considering a stochastic distribution of the two fluids and a classical frequency of interest in seismic experiments, we obtain P-wave attenuation and phase velocity as functions of the fracture gas saturation. This approach could be of interest for the remote detection and quantification of pore fluids using seismic waves.

Key words: Fracture and flow – Seismic anisotropy – Numerical modelling – Acoustic properties

1 INTRODUCTION

Fractures are ubiquitous throughout the Earth's upper crust, and they exert a strong influence on the mechanical and hydraulic properties of the affected rock masses. In particular, open fractures tend to be oriented normal to the direction of minimum *in situ* compressive stress (Schoenberg & Sayers 1995) and, thus, most reservoirs are believed to contain at least one set of subvertical fractures (Liu & Martinez 2012). The seismic method is a valuable tool for the detection and characterization of fractures, due to the fact that seismic waves experience strong directional dependence, and are also significantly attenuated and delayed when propagating through fractured media (Maultzsch et al. 2003). For this reason, there is currently great interest in improving the understanding of seismic wave propagation through fractured rocks in general, and in presence of subvertical fractures in particular (Liu et al. 2000; Liu & Martinez 2012). Further knowledge on this topic could find applications in a large number of disciplines, including groundwater and contaminant hydrology, nuclear waste storage, CO₂ sequestration, hydrocarbon exploration and production, and volcano and earthquake monitoring, among others.

Due to the particularly strong mechanical contrast typically existing between open fractures and their surrounding porous background, seismic waves can induce strong fluid pressure gradients between such media. These pressure gradients are equilibrated through local pore fluid pressure diffusion causing energy dissipation through viscous friction, a phenomenon that manifests itself as attenuation

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and velocity dispersion of the propagating seismic wave (Brajanovski et al. 2006). While a large number of publications explore this physical mechanism in the case of fractured rocks fully saturated by a single porous fluid (Caspari et al. 2016; Chapman 2009; Krzikalla & Müller 2011; Rubino et al. 2013a), the case of partially-saturated fractured rocks, that is, in presence of a second immiscible saturating fluid phase, has not been addressed in depth in the literature. Brajanovski et al. (2010) proposed a model considering that the background contains a patchy distribution of fluids and, also, hosts periodic monosaturated and aligned fractures. Despite being one of the first works accounting for the effects of partial saturation and fracture presence on the seismic signatures of porous rocks, the considered fluid distribution is not realistic. Fractures constitute paths of comparatively low capillary entry pressures and, thus, nonwetting fluid phases, such as gas or CO₂, have a tendency to saturate them rather than the embedding porous background, which, in turn, tends to remain saturated with the wetting phase (e.g., brine). Kong et al. (2013) studied the P-wave dispersion and attenuation in rocks composed of a water-saturated porous background comprising a set of planar aligned fractures, that are saturated by an effective fluid mixture. They observe that the compliance of the effective fluid saturating the fractures determines if FPD effects between fractures and background are suppressed or even reversed as compared with water-saturated fractured environments. However, Kong et al. (2013) consider that all the fractures are saturated with the same type of fluids. It is well known that fracture distributions are often characterized by a large number of lengths and apertures which, in turn, imply that they are associated with different effective permeability values. Due to capillary forces, the non-wetting phase tends to occupy the most permeable fractures, that is, those having larger apertures, whereas the wetting fluid phase saturates the remaining ones. This, in other words, implies that fractures can be saturated by different fluids, a situation that, as far as the authors know, has not been explored thoroughly. One of the few exceptions is the work of Solazzi et al. (2020), where the authors analyze seismic attenuation and phase velocity dispersion in rocks containing partially saturated interconnected stochastic fracture networks. While this work has provided some interesting features on the seismic response of these environments, a systematic analysis of the physical mechanism leading to seismic attenuation and dispersion is still missing.

In this work we study the seismic signatures of porous rocks containing aligned planar fractures, which can be saturated by either of two immiscible fluids, such as water and gas. To do this, we first propose a numerical methodology to obtain the seismic signatures of P-waves travelling perpendicular to a set of parallel, planar fractures. Next, we apply the methodology for analyzing the case of regular distributions of periodic fractures alternatively saturated by the two fluids, and we also explore the role played by the bulk modulus of the involved fluids. Finally, we analyze the case of a regular distribution

Figure 1. (a) Schematic illustration of a periodic fractured medium and (b) the oscillatory relaxation test applied on a corresponding REV. The gray and white regions represent background and fractures, respectively.

of fractures stochastically saturated by gas and water, and determine how the properties of the seismic waves change as a function of the nonwetting fluid phase saturation.

2 METHODOLOGY

In order to obtain the seismic properties of P-waves travelling in a direction normal to a set of parallel, planar fractures, we follow a methodology similar to that proposed by Barbosa et al. (2018). However, instead of solving the resulting equations through a finite-element approach, we employ analytical expressions for the involved variables and obtain the response of the sample through the solution of a system of linear equations. That is, we represent the fractures as highly compliant and permeable porous inclusions embedded in a stiffer and less permeable porous matrix. We then choose a *representative elementary volume* (REV) of the fractured formation, and apply a numerical upscaling procedure to obtain an effective complex-valued and frequency-dependent P-wave modulus which, in turn, allows to compute the attenuation and phase velocity of the seismic wave as functions of frequency.

Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of an REV of a periodic fractured medium of interest. The REV consists on a distribution of N layers, and both the apertures of the fractures and the separation between consecutive fractures are much smaller than the seismic wavelengths. This implies that scattering effects do not play any role and, instead, the presence of the fractures produce a velocity reduction, in addition to attenuation and velocity dispersion as a result of FPD. Emulating the effects of a passing P monochromatic wave, we apply an oscillatory relaxation experiment to the REV, that is, we impose time-harmonic solid displacements normal to the boundaries (Fig. 1b). The resulting stress and strain fields in the sample are obtained by solving the equations of consolidation of Biot (1941). The reasoning for choosing consolidation equations is that, for frequencies much smaller than Biot's critical frequency, the physical process is controlled by fluid-pressure diffusion and, thus, inertial effects can be neglected.

For the considered case, that is, a deformation applied normally to a set of planar fractures, plane-strain conditions are satisfied. Hence, considering the equations in the space-frequency domain and assuming that the fractures are normal to the x -axis, the stress equilibrium within the sample and Darcy's law should be satisfied locally, that is (Biot 1941),

$$\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$-\frac{\partial p_f}{\partial x} = i\omega \frac{\eta}{\kappa} w, \quad (2)$$

where σ is the corresponding component of the total stress tensor, p_f the pore fluid pressure, η the dynamic viscosity of the fluid, κ the permeability, w the average relative fluid displacement, and ω the angular frequency. These equations are coupled through the constitutive relations of poroelasticity, which, in the 1D case under consideration, can be written as (Biot 1941),

$$\sigma = H \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \alpha M \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}, \quad (3)$$

$$p_f = -\alpha M \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - M \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}, \quad (4)$$

where u is the x -component of the average displacement vector of the solid phase, M the Biot modulus, α the Biot effective stress coefficient, and H the undrained plane wave modulus. These parameters are given by (Bourbié et al. 1987)

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{K_m}{K_s}, \quad (5)$$

$$M = \left(\frac{\alpha - \phi}{K_s} + \frac{\phi}{K_f} \right)^{-1}, \quad (6)$$

$$H = K_m + \frac{4}{3}\mu + M\alpha^2, \quad (7)$$

where K_s and K_m denote the bulk moduli of the solid grains and of the dry matrix, K_f the bulk modulus of the pore fluid, μ the shear modulus of the dry frame, and ϕ the porosity of the poroelastic material.

We consider the REV defined by the interval $[0, L]$, where $L > 0$. In this domain, we have the partition $\{x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{N-1}, x_N\}$, where $x_0 = 0$ and $x_N = L$. Each interval $[x_{j-1}, x_j]$, with $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$, represents the j -th layer of the rock, which can be related to background material between two fractures, or to a fracture saturated with one of the two immiscible fluids. Please note that fractures are not necessarily equidistant. Let u_j , w_j , σ_j and p_j scalar functions that represent the average solid displacement, the average relative fluid displacement, the total stress tensor, and the fluid pressure within the interval $[x_{j-1}, x_j]$. As the physical properties in the considered layer are constant, it is straightforward to show that, within each interval, the solution to the set of equations (1)-(4) is

given by

$$w_j(x, \omega) = A_j e^{(k_j(x-x_j))} + B_j e^{(k_j(x-x_j))}, \quad (8)$$

$$u_j(x, \omega) = \frac{\sigma}{H_j} x - \frac{\alpha_j M_j}{H_j} w_j(x, \omega) + C_j, \quad (9)$$

$$p_j(x, \omega) = -\alpha_j M_j \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x}(x, \omega) - M_j \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x}(x, \omega), \quad (10)$$

where $k_j = \sqrt{\frac{\omega}{D_j}} \sqrt{i}$, with $D_j = \frac{\kappa_j}{\eta_j} \left(M_j - \frac{\alpha_j^2 M_j^2}{H_j} \right)$ being the diffusion coefficient, and the coefficients A_j, B_j, C_j and D_j are constants to be determined. Please note that, from now on, the subindex i refers to the corresponding property in the interval $[x_{j-1}, x_j]$. Using these expressions and requiring the continuity of u, w, p_f , and σ at the contact between consecutive layers, that is, at x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{N-1} , we get $4(N-1)$ linear equations. In addition, due to the periodicity of the system, at the boundaries of the REV we require $w_1(0) = w_N(x_N), p_1(0) = p_N(x_N)$, together with $u_1(0) = \Delta u/2$ and $u_N(x_N) = -\Delta u/2$. This completes a linear system of $4N$ equations which, in turn, allows to compute the coefficients A_j, B_j, C_j and D_j for the N layers. These coefficients fully describe the behaviour of the layered REV subjected to an oscillatory relaxation test through equations (8)-(10). It is interesting to remark here that, as σ_j is constant within a given layer, the continuity imposed at the contacts between consecutive layers implies that the stress is spatially homogeneous within the REV. We refer to this constant value of stress as σ_{REV} .

The average strain in the sample is given by

$$\langle \epsilon \rangle = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L \frac{du}{dx} dx = \frac{u(L) - u(0)}{L} = -\Delta u/L, \quad (11)$$

where $\langle . \rangle$ denotes the volume average. On the other hand, as the stress is spatially homogeneous within the sample, we have

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \sigma_{REV}. \quad (12)$$

Under the assumption that the average response of the probed REV can be represented by an equivalent homogeneous viscoelastic solid, the average stress and strain can be related through a complex-valued, frequency-dependent effective plane wave modulus $H_{eff}(\omega)$, such that

$$H_{eff} = \frac{\langle \sigma \rangle}{\langle \epsilon \rangle} = -\frac{\sigma_{REV}}{\frac{\Delta u}{L}}. \quad (13)$$

It is important to remark here that the concept of an effective medium assumes that the prevailing seismic wavelengths are much larger than the fracture apertures, the distance between consecutive fractures, and the correlation length of the considered fracture distance distribution.

Once the effective plane wave modulus is obtained, the phase velocity and the inverse quality

factor of P-waves propagating perpendicular to the fracture set are given by (Rubino et al. 2009)

$$V_p(\omega) = (Re(V_{pc}(\omega)^{-1}))^{-1}, \quad (14)$$

$$Q_p^{-1}(\omega) = \frac{Im(V_{pc}^2)}{Re(V_{pc}^2)}, \quad (15)$$

where $V_{pc}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{H_{eff}(\omega)}{\rho_b}}$ is the complex P-wave velocity, and Re and Im are the real and imaginary parts of the corresponding value, respectively.

It is important to remark here that this methodology is computationally convenient, and it allows to handle arbitrary fracture sets and different pore fluids. The assumption of planar fractures, on the other hand, which implies fractures having infinite lateral extension, is strictly valid when the radii of the fractures are much larger than the prevailing wavelengths and the spacing between consecutive fractures (Gurevich et al. 2009).

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

In the following, we propose two scenarios to study the effects of partial saturation on the seismic response of fractured rocks. First, we study a simple case consisting on a medium with parallel fractures, regularly distributed, saturated alternatively by two different fluids: water and gas. We explore the physical reasons for the resulting seismic characteristics and, also, we consider the effect of changing the bulk modulus of the gaseous phase on the seismic response. Finally, we consider the case of a very large number of regularly distributed fractures, randomly saturated by gas or water, and we explore the resulting seismic signatures as functions of the overall saturation of the probed medium.

3.1 Regular distribution of fractures alternately saturated with water and gas

We first consider a porous formation containing a regular distribution of fractures, alternately saturated with gas and water. This is the simplest case and, therefore, we will analyze it thoroughly in order to get a wide understanding of the physical interactions between the fractures and the embedding background as well as between consecutive fractures in presence of two immiscible fluids.

Let us consider an REV of the medium under study, having a length of 41.2 mm and containing two fractures of equal aperture (0.6 mm) spaced at a distance of 20 mm. The fractures are modeled as highly compliant and highly porous and permeable features embedded in a much stiffer and much less porous and permeable background medium. The background is saturated with water, whereas for the fractures we consider that one fracture is saturated with water whereas the other one with gas. We refer to this case as “WG”. For comparison, we also consider a second case (“WW”), for which all the

Background		
L_1	0.02	Layer length [m]
ϕ	0.05	Porosity
κ	10^{-4}	Permeability [D]
K_m	31.5	Frame bulk modulus [GPa]
μ_m	37.4	Frame shear modulus [GPa]
K_s	37	Solid grain bulk modulus [GPa]
ρ_s	2.65	Solid grain density [g/cc]
Fracture		
L_2	0.0006	Aperture [m]
ϕ	0.8	Porosity
κ	1000	Permeability [D]
K_m	0.04	Frame bulk modulus [GPa]
μ_m	0.02	Frame shear modulus [GPa]
K_s	37	Solid grain bulk modulus [GPa]
ρ_s	2.65	Solid grain density [g/cc]
Pore Fluids		
Water ρ_f	1.090	Density [g/cc]
Water η	1	Viscosity [cP]
Water K_f	2.25	Bulk modulus [GPa]
Gas ρ_f	0.078	Density [g/cc]
Gas η	0.15	Viscosity [cP]
Gas K_f	0.012	Bulk modulus [GPa]

Table 1. Physical and geometrical properties employed in the numerical simulations.

fractures are saturated with water. For these simulations we use the physical properties employed by Rubino et al. (2017), as shown in Table 1.

Figure 2a shows the resulting inverse quality factor of P-waves propagating normally to the fractures, as a function of frequency. We observe that in the WW case, there is a single peak with very high levels of attenuation, located at a frequency $f_c \approx 23$ Hz. This attenuation peak is due to energy dissipation in the fluid located in the porous space of the background material, surrounding the fractures, in response to wave-induced FPD between these two media (Rubino et al. 2014). Interestingly, when the fractured sample is partially saturated, two peaks arise: one located at a frequency $f_1 \approx 0.23$ Hz, and a second one, at $f_2 \approx 12$ Hz, of very small amplitude. In comparison with the WW case, we observe

Figure 2. (a) Inverse quality factor and (b) phase velocity as functions of frequency for a P-wave travelling perpendicular to a regular distribution of fractures fully saturated with water (WW) and alternately saturated with water and gas (WG).

that the highest peak is shifted two orders of magnitude towards lower frequencies and its amplitude is slightly reduced. Figure 2b, on the other hand, shows the phase velocity for both cases. By comparing the curves we observe that the presence of gas in some fractures produce an overall, significant velocity drop, which is due to the very high compressibility of gas in comparison with water. In addition, and as expected according to the behaviour of the attenuation curves, the WW case manifests strong velocity dispersion for frequencies around f_c , whereas the WG case shows comparatively smaller but still noticeable dispersion for frequencies around f_1 and rather negligible dispersion around f_2 .

In order to understand the physical reasons for the differences observed between the two attenuation curves, we plot the local energy dissipation. The dissipated power quantifies the energy being lost in the system per unit time. In the case of fluid-saturated porous materials, energy dissipation is due to viscous friction and, consequently, its magnitude strongly depends on the average relative motion between the fluid and the solid. The dissipated power per unit volume averaged over one wave cycle is given by (Rubino et al. 2014)

$$\langle P_V(x, \omega) \rangle = \frac{\omega^2}{2} \frac{\eta(x)}{\kappa(x)} \|w(x, \omega)\|^2. \quad (16)$$

Figure 3 shows the dissipated power for the characteristic frequencies, obtained using Eq. (16). We observe in Figure 3a that, in the WW case, most energy dissipation occurs in the background, mainly in the vicinity of the fractures, whereas energy dissipation is zero at the midpoint between consecutive fractures. This behaviour is expected (Rubino et al. 2014) and can be understood as follows: when the seismic perturbation compresses the medium, the fluid pressure inside the fractures is much higher than the corresponding fluid pressure in the background due to the contrasting compliances of the two media. The resulting pressure gradient generates fluid flow from the fractures into the background during the compressive cycle, and in the opposite direction during the extensive one. The associated

Figure 3. Dissipated power per unit volume averaged over one wave cycle as a function of the position within the REV, computed at the corresponding characteristic frequencies for (a) the WW case and (b, c) the WG case. Yellow and cyan segments denote the corresponding positions of the fractures saturated with gas and water, respectively.

viscous friction in the background generates energy dissipation, which is maximum next to the fractures, where the pressure gradient is also maximum, and zero in the midpoint between the fractures, as due to the symmetry of the problem fluid velocity is zero. It should also be noted that energy dissipation inside the fractures is negligible, which is a consequence of the very high permeability of this medium in comparison with that of the background (see Eq. 16). The fluid pressure relaxation in the background material is governed by fluid pressure diffusion, with a characteristic transition angular frequency ω_c . At this characteristic frequency, the diffusion length, L_d , is similar to the characteristic size a_{meso} of the heterogeneities, so that (Rubino et al. 2013b)

$$L_d \equiv \sqrt{\frac{D}{\omega_c}} = a_{meso}, \quad (17)$$

where the pressure diffusivity D can be expressed as

$$D = \frac{\kappa}{\eta} \left(M - \frac{\alpha^2 M^2}{H} \right). \quad (18)$$

Using the physical parameters corresponding to the background material, where most energy dissipation takes place, and using Eq. (17) with $\omega_c = 2\pi f_c$, we get for the WW case, $a_{meso} = 5.2$ mm, that is, a quarter of the separation between consecutive fractures. This result is in agreement with

other works where the critical frequency has been explored in the context of the classical White's model (Carcione & Picotti 2006).

Figure 3c shows that, in the WG case, the dissipation pattern occurring for the frequency of the lowest attenuation peak f_2 is quite comparable to the behaviour observed for the WW case, suggesting that a similar physical process is responsible for the small bump seen in the attenuation curve at such frequency. Indeed, the corresponding characteristic frequency of the two cases are similar, supporting this hypothesis. The reason why the overall energy dissipation and, thus, related seismic attenuation at the frequency f_2 is less significant in the WG case is because gas is a much more compressible fluid as compared to water. This, in turn implies that the pressure change inside the gas saturated fractures in response to the seismic perturbation is much less important in comparison with the water-saturated case and, therefore, the resulting local pressure gradient and corresponding viscous dissipation are less significant. The dissipation pattern shown in Figure 3b for the frequency of the highest attenuation peak (f_1), on the other hand, is very different and, indeed, as far as the authors know, this is the first of its kind shown in the literature. We observe that energy dissipation also occurs in the background in this case, and it is maximum in the regions next to the fracture saturated with water. However, the level of dissipation decreases slowly and monotonically within the background until it reaches the gas-saturated fracture. Using the physical parameters corresponding to the background material and Eq. (17) with $\omega_c = 2\pi f_1$, we get $a_{meso} = 52$ mm, that is, a_{meso} turns out to be equal to 2.5 times the separation between consecutive fractures, approximately. This shows that the simple relation between characteristic size of the heterogeneities and the diffusion length does not apply in this particular case.

In order to shed some light on the behaviours shown in Figure 3 and, in particular, on the dissipation pattern corresponding to the frequency of the main attenuation peak of the WG case, we illustrate in Figure 4 the real part of the relative fluid displacement (w) as a function of the position within the REV. This quantity corresponds, in time domain, to the state of the fluid at the time of the maximum compression imposed on the sample if the applied deformation is given by $Re(\Delta u e^{i\omega t})$. The arrows shown in the figure indicate the direction of relative fluid motion at the contact between the fractures and the embedding background, as dictated by the sign of the real part of w . We observe in Figure 4a that, in the WW case, when the applied compression is maximum, fluid flows from the fractures into the background, as expected. A similar behaviour can be seen in figure 4c for the WG case at the frequency f_2 , indicating that for this frequency the fluid pressure induced inside both fractures is greater than that in the surrounding background material. The fact that the gas inside the fractures attain pressure values higher than the fluid pressure in the background region next to them can, in principle, seem to be counterintuitive. However, this higher pressure is due to the very strong deformation of the fracture material, together with the very stiff properties of the background, which do not permit

Figure 4. Real part of the relative fluid displacement as a function of the position within the REV, for (a) the WW case and (b, c) the WG case, computed at the corresponding characteristic frequencies. The arrows indicate the direction of the relative fluid displacement at the contact between the fractures and the embedding background. Yellow and cyan segments denote the corresponding positions of the fractures saturated with gas and water, respectively.

that the pore fluid in the background to increase the pressure significantly. Figure 4b, on the other hand, shows a very particular behaviour for the frequency of the largest attenuation peak, f_1 : while the fluid flows from the water-saturated fractures towards the embedding background, it flows in the opposite direction at the boundaries of the fractures saturated with gas, that is, from the background into the fractures. These two contrasting behaviours at the frequencies f_1 and f_2 can be understood as follows: in the case of the frequency f_2 , the fluid pressure inside the gas-saturated fractures is higher than that in the adjacent background material, and the fluid pressure diffusion initiated in the water-saturated background does not have enough time to reach the gas-saturated fractures in a half cycle of oscillation. For these reasons, for this frequency the fluid flows from the gas-saturated fractures into the background during the compressive cycle of the applied strain. However, for the frequency f_1 , the fluid pressure diffusion generated at the water-saturated fractures has enough time to reach the gas-saturated fractures and, in such a case, the fluid pressure in the background material in the vicinity of the gas saturated fractures reach pressure values much higher than inside them. This, in turn, implies that the flow direction is from the background into the gas-saturated fractures for this lower frequency.

Figure 5. (a) Inverse quality factor and (b) phase velocity as functions of frequency for a P-wave travelling perpendicular to a regular distribution of fractures alternately saturated with water and gas. Line colors indicate the responses considering different values for the gas bulk modulus.

This particular fluid pressure pattern generates very intense oscillatory fluid flow and, consequently, the corresponding seismic attenuation is very significant, as can be seen in Figure 2.

To corroborate our physical interpretation of the two manifestations of FPD observed in partially-saturated fractured rocks, we now explore the role played by the compressibility of the gas in the response of the fractured medium. In order to do this, we employ the same REV as before, and the same physical properties provided in Table 1, except for the bulk modulus of gas. For this parameter, we consider three different values: 0.0012, 0.012, and 0.12 GPa. Please note that the intermediate compressibility of 0.012 GPa was used in Figures 2, 3 and 4. Figure 5 shows the resulting seismic attenuation and phase velocity curves as functions of frequency. We observe that, for the highest bulk modulus the attenuation curve has two peaks, whereas for lower values the peak located at f_2 is rather negligible. Taking into account that the associated energy dissipation is due to fluid pressure diffusion from both the gas- and water-saturated fractures to the background, this behaviour is expected. Indeed, as the fracture gas gets a higher bulk modulus, its increase of pressure in response to the deformation will be more significant, and so it will be the associated fluid pressure gradient and fluid flow. In the case of the attenuation peak located at the frequency f_1 , we observe that it gets higher as the gas bulk modulus gets lower values. This makes sense with the provided interpretation of the associated FPD manifestation, since a lower fracture gas bulk modulus increases the pressure gradient between the gas saturated fractures and the adjacent background region affected by the FPD initiated at the contiguous water-saturated fractures. It is important to remark here that the two transition frequencies remain almost unaffected by the bulk modulus of the gas, which is due to the fact that the region where most of the energy dissipation occurs is the water-saturated background.

Figure 5b shows the resulting P-wave phase velocity as a function of frequency. We observe that as the bulk modulus of the gas decreases, there is an overall velocity drop of the curves. This is expected,

since as gas is more compressible the fractured rock becomes softer. In addition, for frequencies in the vicinities of f_1 and f_2 , P-wave velocity manifests dispersion which, as expected, tends to be more significant when the associated inverse quality factor gets higher values.

3.2 Regular distribution of fractures stochastically saturated by gas and water

In order to analyze the influence of the distribution of gas and water in the fractures of a given formation and its overall saturation, in this subsection we consider stochastic distributions of two fluids saturating a large number of fractures. That is, we consider an REV with a very large number of regularly distributed fractures of equal aperture (0.6 mm), separated by background material of constant thickness (20 mm) and the fractures can be saturated by water or gas. We define the overall gas saturation of the probed fracture system as

$$S = \frac{N_f^g}{N_f}, \quad (19)$$

where N_f^g and N_f denote the number of fractures saturated with gas and the total number of fractures contained in the REV, respectively. Considering $S \in \{0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9\}$, for each level of saturation, we randomly choose from the REV $S \times N_f$ fractures and we consider them to be saturated with gas, and the remaining ones, with water. The seismic responses are computed using the physical properties provided in Table 1. In order to assure that the resulting seismic signatures are representative for that level of saturation, we perform a convergence analysis: For each gas saturation value S , we progressively increase the size of the REV and, thus, the number of fractures, and compute the seismic signatures as a function of the total number of fractures. Convergence is reached when these parameters stabilize at quasi-constant values. For $S \leq 0.3$, REV's with 10.000 fractures were needed, whereas for the other levels of saturation, REV's with 1000 fractures were sufficient to satisfy such condition.

Figure 6 shows the resulting seismic attenuation and phase velocity as functions of frequency, for different values of overall gas saturation. We observe in Figure 6a that, in all cases, the inverse quality factor presents two distinctive peaks and, independently of the gas saturation value, the second peak tends to be lower than the first one. The location of the high-frequency peak is rather insensitive to the gas saturation value, and it is located at a frequency of around 11 Hz. The height of this attenuation peak increases as the overall gas saturation is reduced. This is expected as, based on our previous analysis, this attenuation peak is due to FPD processes initiated at consecutive fractures that interact in the background material. When a fracture is saturated with water, the resulting fluid pressure gradients reach higher values in comparison with a gas saturated fracture. Consequently, when the number of water saturated fractures increases, the second attenuation peak gets higher values. In the case

Figure 6. (a) Inverse quality and (b) phase velocity as functions of frequency for a P-wave travelling perpendicular to a regular distribution of fractures stochastically saturated with water and gas. Line colours indicate the responses for different levels of overall gas saturation, S .

of the peak located at lower frequencies, on the other hand, the corresponding transition frequency seems to slightly shifts towards lower frequencies as the overall gas saturation is reduced. Indeed, further inspection allows to observe that the transition frequency is reduced from around 0.2 Hz for $S = 0.9$ to 0.05 Hz for $S = 0.1$. In addition, we can notice that the levels of attenuation progressively increases as the gas saturation is reduced from 0.9 to 0.3. However, when S is further reduced to 0.1, the attenuation peak is slightly reduced. Based on our previous analysis, we can conclude that this attenuation peak is due to energy dissipation occurring in the background material between two consecutive fractures saturated with differing fluids (gas or water). The relation between overall gas saturation and attenuation level in this case is not simple. For low values of S , gas saturated fractures are more likely to be surrounded by water saturated fractures and, thus, the attenuation level is expected to increase as we replace water by gas in some fractures. However, as the value of S further increases, the replacement of water by gas in some fractures can act in the opposite direction, since fractures with water next to fractures with gas are needed for this FPD manifestation. At the same time, it has to be taken into account that not only energy dissipation is involved in the definition of the inverse quality factor, that is, the strain energy of the system also plays an important role in this context (Solazzi et al. 2016).

Figure 6(b) shows the resulting P-wave phase velocity as a function of frequency. We observe that as the value of S increases, there is an overall velocity drop of the curves. This is expected, since the total amount of fractures containing gas is larger, the rock becomes softer. In addition, for frequencies in the vicinities of f_1 and f_2 the velocities manifest dispersion which, as expected, tends to be more significant when the associated inverse quality factor gets higher values.

An interesting aspect of the proposed methodology for exploring stochastic distributions of gas and water in fractured rocks, is the fact that the acoustic properties can be computed, for a certain

Figure 7. (a) Inverse quality factor and (b) phase velocity as functions of the overall gas saturation of fractures for a P-wave travelling perpendicular to a regular distribution of fractures stochastically saturated with water and gas. The employed frequency is of 30Hz .

frequency of interest, as a function of the overall gas saturation of the probed formation. This can be of interest in applications where the detection of different fluids and their volume quantifications are important tasks. To illustrate the potential of this approach, we show in Figure 7 the inverse quality factor and phase velocity as functions of the overall gas saturation, for a typical seismic frequency of 30 Hz. We observe that both, attenuation and phase velocity, tend to decrease with increasing values of S . This kind of attenuation- and velocity-saturation relationships which, as far as the authors know, are not available in the literature for the explored environments, could be used in the seismic characterization of a fractured reservoir, to infer the regions predominantly saturated by gas or other compressible fluid (such as CO_2).

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have explored the attenuation and phase velocity of P-waves traveling perpendicularly to a set of planar, parallel fractures that can be saturated with either water or gas, and embedded in a water-saturated porous homogeneous background. One of the main conclusions of this study is that two manifestations of FPD arise in these scenarios. One of them, associated with relatively high levels of attenuation, is due to FPD between consecutive fractures saturated with different fluids. In such case, the FPD process initiates at a fracture saturated with water, and reaches a consecutive fracture saturated with gas. For this reason, maximum attenuation associated with this FPD manifestation occurs at an intermediate value of overall gas saturation, while it gets lower values as the fractured formation approaches the fully water- or gas-saturated limit. The second FPD manifestation, on the other hand, occurs at higher frequencies, is characterized by lower values of seismic attenuation, and is due to the interaction in the background of FPD processes initiated at consecutive fractures. Consequently, the height of the associated attenuation peak increases as the overall gas saturation is reduced,

since water-saturated fractures produce stronger fluid pressure gradients and, thus, dissipation than gas-saturated fractures. This analysis was restricted to P-waves propagating perpendicularly to the considered fractures. However, it is possible to extend the methodology to consider arbitrary azimuths and incidence angles. In order to do this, the low- and high-frequency limits of the components of the effective stiffness matrix can be computed using the anisotropic Gassmann's equations (Guo et al. 2017). Next, the frequency-dependent plane wave modulus obtained in this work can be used to define a branching function that allows to connect the before-mentioned low- and high frequency limits, thus providing a frequency-dependent, complex-valued effective stiffness matrix (Krzikalla & Müller 2011). This procedure would allow to explore the impact of the two FPD manifestations explored in this work on the anisotropic characteristics of the partially-saturated fractured formation, a task that will be considered in future works.

A conceptual simplification used in this work is that it is based on a one-dimensional analysis, which implies that the fractures are infinite planes perpendicular to the considered axis. This limitation is also responsible for the low velocity values in presence of gas-saturated fractures. The quasi-planar nature of many fractures and their tendency to form sets of vertical parallel fractures in the Earth's upper crust partially justifies this assumption and, hence, provides valuable insights into the FPD manifestations expected to prevail in real fracture systems. In the future, we will extend the analysis to sets of partially-saturated finite-size, parallel fractures through the use of 3D numerical simulations (He et al. 2022).

The analysis presented in this work does not only provide additional insights from a theoretical perspective, but also can have an impact on practical applications related with seismic characterization of partially saturated fractured rocks. In this sense, we have shown that the characteristic frequency of the main attenuation peak expected in this context does not follow the classical formula relating the diffusion length and characteristic size of the involved heterogeneities (Eq. 17). This, in turn, shows that the two manifestations of FPD described in this work should be taken into account when interpreting seismic data from these environments. Moreover, by considering a stochastic distribution of the two fluids, the methodology allowed us to obtain P-wave seismic velocity and attenuation as a function of overall gas saturation, relationships that can be very useful to infer the regions of a given fractured formation predominantly saturated by gas or other compressible fluid.

5 DATA AVAILABILITY

Experimental and observational data were neither used nor created for this research. Mathematical expressions to replicate the results of this article are available in the article.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported partially by the European Commission, through the DISCO2 STORE project, Grant agreement ID: 101007851 of the Horizon 2020 Programme. N.N.S. acknowledges the financial support received from the National Argentine University of Comahue. The authors acknowledge the financial support received from CONICET (PIP 1122021010034600).

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